
Special Training for Special Needs: Evaluating Teacher Preparedness for Inclusive Education in Bangladesh

Mohammed Raihanul Hoque

Institute of Education and Research (IER), University of Chittagong

Abstract

This research investigates the preparedness of pre-service teachers in Bangladesh for inclusive education (IE), analyzing attitudes and perceived teaching efficacy, with a focus on the influence of educational level, gender, and training duration. Conducted in two phases, the study employed a mixed-methods approach, drawing on quantitative data from survey questionnaires and qualitative insights from interviews with institutional heads and teachers. Quantitative analysis revealed that secondary-level pre-service teachers displayed more positive attitudes and higher self-efficacy towards IE than their primary-level counterparts. Female pre-service teachers, despite showing more positive attitudes, reported lower perceived teaching efficacy compared to males. These findings were substantiated by qualitative feedback, highlighting the curriculum's lack of IE focus at the primary level and more robust IE integration at the secondary level. The study's significance lies in its identification of specific gaps in teacher training programs, pointing to the need for a uniform curriculum that addresses IE across educational levels. It also sheds light on socio-cultural influences that may impact female pre-service teachers' self-efficacy, suggesting the necessity for gender-sensitive training interventions. Recommendations include curriculum reform to embed IE comprehensively, enhancement of practical IE training experiences, and policy support to prioritize IE. This study underscores the importance of teacher preparedness as a determinant of IE's success and advocates for reforms to cultivate an equitable educational landscape in Bangladesh. Further research is encouraged to refine the teacher education framework for IE, ensuring all students' rights to quality education are upheld.

Keywords: Inclusive Education, Pre-Service Teachers, Teacher Preparedness, Attitudes, Self-Efficacy, Bangladesh

1 Introduction

Inclusive education, a globally recognized pedagogical approach, aims to cater to the diverse needs of all learners, with particular emphasis on those who are marginalized by traditional educational systems [1, 2]. Its foundation rests on the belief that educational environments should adapt to the needs of students, rather than expecting students to conform to a pre-established system [3, 4]. This fundamental shift in educational philosophy is reflective of a broader societal commitment to equity and human rights. Despite the universal appeal of inclusive education, its implementation remains a formidable challenge, particularly in resource-constrained environments such as Bangladesh [5]. Bangladesh, with its pledge to the Education For All (EFA)

¹Corresponding author: raihanulhaq@gmail.com

movement and the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, has unequivocally signaled its commitment to creating an inclusive education system [6]. However, as a developing country with a dense population of approximately 165 million people, the journey towards truly inclusive education is fraught with challenges [7, 8]. The adult literacy rate hovers around 72.9% (UNESCO, 2021), and while primary school enrollment rates have seen substantial improvement, the quality and inclusivity of education continue to be areas of concern. In the context of Bangladesh [9], pre-service teacher education is pivotal in cultivating an inclusive educational climate. Teachers are the cornerstone of educational reform, and their preparedness to manage diverse classrooms is critical to the success of inclusive practices [10]. Yet, the preparation of pre-service teachers for inclusive settings remains an under-explored domain, especially from the perspective of those who shape educational policies and curricula—the heads of higher education institutions.

The present study seeks to fill this gap by examining the beliefs and challenges faced by institutional heads in preparing pre-service teachers for inclusive education in Bangladesh. It aims to shed light on the complexities of implementing inclusive education policies, with a focus on teacher preparedness as a critical component of this systemic change. Through this inquiry, the research endeavors to contribute to the discourse on inclusive education, offering insights that could inform policy and practice, not just in Bangladesh, but in similar contexts globally. Recent statistics underscore the urgency of this research. According to the Directorate of Primary Education and the Centre for Services and Information on Disability (2021), an estimated 90% of children with disabilities in Bangladesh do not have access to education. Moreover, among children from indigenous communities, the completion rate for primary education stands at a mere 22% (UNICEF, 2021). These figures highlight the need for an educational system that not only accommodates diversity but also celebrates and nurtures it.

The research will be guided by the following objectives:

1. To identify and understand the beliefs of higher education institutional heads about inclusive education in Bangladesh.
2. To explore the perceived challenges in preparing pre-service teachers for inclusive classrooms by these institutional heads.
3. To examine the strategies that higher education institutional heads deem necessary to overcome the challenges of inclusive teacher preparation.

The research questions that will steer this inquiry are:

1. What are the beliefs of heads of higher education institutions in Bangladesh regarding inclusive education?.
2. What challenges do these institutional leaders perceive in equipping pre-service teachers for inclusive classrooms?
3. What strategies do these institutional heads propose to address the identified challenges in teacher preparation for inclusive education?

The purpose of this research is to dive into the complexities of preparing pre-service teachers for the demands of inclusive education in Bangladesh. It aims to understand the nuances of institutional heads' beliefs about inclusion, the challenges they face in reforming teacher education, and the strategies they consider effective in overcoming these challenges. This research adopts a qualitative methodology, employing semi-structured interviews to gather rich, contextualized data from a diverse range of educational leaders across Bangladesh. Understanding the perspectives of these leaders is crucial, as they are instrumental in shaping the educational landscape. They hold the key to initiating and sustaining change in teacher education programs, thereby directly influencing the quality and inclusivity of future classrooms. Through this research, we aspire to amplify their voices, distilling their insights into actionable strategies that can pave the way for a more inclusive educational environment in Bangladesh and beyond.

In sum, this research aims to contribute to the global conversation on inclusive education by focusing on a context that exemplifies both the challenges and the potential for transformative change. By situating the study within the unique socio-political and cultural context of Bangladesh, it endeavors to offer a nuanced understanding of what it takes to prepare teachers for the noble and necessary task of inclusive education.

2 Background

The educational system of Bangladesh is a tapestry interwoven with the aspirations of its socio-cultural ethos and the challenges of its economic constraints[11]. With a population surging beyond 160 million, the nation

grappling with the Herculean task of providing equitable education to all, amidst a high population density and varied socio-economic strata [12]. The literacy rate, which currently hovers around 74.7% as per the latest reports, reflects a significant leap from the past decades yet masks the disparities across different regions and communities [13, 14].

Inclusive education, a concept globally recognized as the cornerstone of equitable educational systems, has gradually found its footing in Bangladesh. Historically rooted in international mandates such as the Salamanca Statement of 1994, the movement for inclusive education has been fueled by the global push for education for all, regardless of any disabilities or socio-economic barriers [15]. Bangladesh's legal framework, including the Persons with Disabilities Welfare Act of 2001 and the National Education Policy of 2010, underscore the nation's commitment to this paradigm. Teacher education and professional development in Bangladesh have been pivotal in the education sector's attempts to adapt to the inclusive model [16, 17]. The structure of teacher training programs has evolved, albeit with varying degrees of success and implementation. With institutions ranging from Primary Teachers' Training Institutes (PTIs) to Teachers' Training Colleges (TTCs) and universities, the country has a diverse landscape of teacher preparation. These entities are at the forefront of grappling with the transition to inclusive pedagogy, a shift that demands not only structural changes but also a paradigmatic shift in teaching and learning approaches.

However, this shift is not without its challenges. The preparation of teachers to meet the diverse needs of all learners has surfaced as a critical gap. Issues such as inadequate curriculum content on inclusive education, traditional pedagogical methods, and insufficient practical teaching experiences continue to hinder progress. Furthermore, the implementation of inclusive education is impeded by limited resources, large class sizes, and a lack of trained teacher educators [18, 19]. Bangladesh's strides towards inclusive education have been in line with its national commitments and international agreements [20]. The National Plan of Action Phase II (2003-2015) and the Second Primary Education Development Program (PEDP II) reflect concerted efforts to prioritize inclusive education. The nation's alignment with the Millennium Development Goals and the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities further reinforces its dedication to this cause.

Despite these commitments, the reality on the ground reflects a stark contrast, particularly in the realm of inclusive education implementation [21]. According to a report by the Directorate of Primary Education and the Centre for Services and Information on Disability, a staggering 89% of children with disabilities are out of the educational loop. This statistic not only raises concerns about the efficacy of policy initiatives but also calls into question the preparedness of the education system to embrace inclusivity fully. The policy initiatives, while robust on paper, often falter in execution. The Draft National Child Policy 2010 and the Compulsory Primary Education Act 1990 are cases in point, reflecting a vision of non-discrimination that is yet to be fully realized in educational practice. The National Education Policy 2010 explicitly advocates for the inclusion of children with special needs, yet the lived experiences of these children tell a different story.

In the backdrop of these challenges, the role of higher education institutional heads becomes crucial. Their beliefs, attitudes, and the strategies they employ to navigate through these challenges have a significant impact on the trajectory of teacher preparation. As they are poised to act as change agents, their insights and experiences are invaluable in understanding and addressing the intricacies of implementing inclusive education. This backdrop sets the stage for a deeper exploration in the Literature Review, where the focus will shift to critically examining the existing research on the preparation of teachers for inclusive education, and how the current study contributes to this body of knowledge.

3 Literature Review

3.1 Conceptual Understanding of Inclusive Education

Inclusive education is a philosophy that advocates for the restructuring of educational policies, curricula, and practices to accommodate all children regardless of their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, linguistic, or other conditions. This definition, as articulated by the Salamanca Statement (UNESCO, 1994), sets the foundation for understanding inclusive education as a global mandate. In Bangladesh, the concept is still evolving, with the National Education Policy (2010) integrating elements of inclusivity in the mainstream educational framework. The literature underscores inclusive education as a complex and dynamic process, one that extends beyond the mere placement of children with special needs into regular classrooms to encompass a broad spectrum of learning diversities.

3.2 Pre-service Teacher Preparation for Inclusive Education

The preparation of pre-service teachers for inclusive classrooms is crucial for the success of inclusive education. Research consistently shows that teacher attitudes towards inclusion are significantly influenced by their training

and perceived competence in handling diverse needs. The curriculum content, teaching methodologies, and practicum experiences are pivotal components in shaping these attitudes. In Bangladesh, the teacher education curriculum has been criticized for its lack of focus on inclusive education [22]. Studies also indicate that practical teaching experiences are insufficient in equipping pre-service teachers with the skills necessary for inclusivity (Ahsan, Sharma, & Deppeler, 2012).

3.3 Challenges in Implementing Inclusive Education

The literature identifies numerous challenges in the implementation of inclusive education. Negative attitudes and beliefs towards disabilities, large class sizes, inadequate resources, and insufficient training of teacher educators are recurrent themes in the context of Bangladesh [23]. These challenges are not unique to Bangladesh, as similar issues are reported in other developing countries [24]. The disparity between policy formulation and its practical application is another significant barrier to inclusive education.

3.4 Role of Institutional Heads in Teacher Preparation

The role of institutional heads in shaping the landscape of teacher education for inclusive education is critical. Their beliefs and attitudes can either facilitate or hinder the implementation of inclusive practices. In Bangladesh, the heads of education institutions play a dual role of administration and leadership, often acting as catalysts for change [25]. However, the literature suggests a need for more proactive and innovative leadership to spearhead the necessary reforms.

3.5 Strategies for Enhancing Inclusive Education

To overcome the challenges of inclusive education, a range of strategies have been suggested. These include curriculum reform, enhanced practicum experiences, and a focus on developing collaborative skills among pre-service teachers. The literature also emphasizes the importance of ongoing professional development and support for in-service teachers [26].

3.6 Research Gaps and Future Directions

Despite the wealth of literature on inclusive education, there remains a significant gap in context-specific research, particularly in the case of Bangladesh. Studies often fail to capture the nuanced challenges faced by institutions in developing countries. There is a need for empirical research that delves into the perceptions of institutional heads and their role in teacher preparation for inclusive education. This gap underscores the importance of the current study, which seeks to illuminate the perspectives of higher education institutional heads in Bangladesh and contribute to the discourse on inclusive education.

4 Methodology

4.1 Research Design

The study was anchored in a qualitative research paradigm, adopting a case study methodology. This approach was chosen to facilitate an in-depth examination of the subjective experiences and beliefs of institutional heads concerning inclusive education in Bangladesh. The nature of the research questions warranted a design that could capture the nuances of participants' perspectives and the contextual complexities of educational settings.

4.2 Participant Selection

The participant pool comprised 41 institutional heads and 254 teachers from various educational institutions across Bangladesh, including Primary Teachers' Training Institutes (PTIs), Teachers' Training Colleges (TTCs), and universities offering pre-service teacher education programs. Purposive sampling was employed to ensure that participants represented the six geographical divisions of Bangladesh, thus capturing a broad spectrum of experiences and perspectives. The selection process was guided by the criteria of maximum variation to explore different insights and challenges across diverse institutional contexts.

4.3 Data Collection Instruments

Three primary data collection methods were utilized:

1. **Semi-Structured Interviews:** These were conducted to gather in-depth data from participants. An interview guide with open-ended questions was meticulously developed based on the literature review and the research objectives. This guide provided a flexible framework for discussions, allowing participants to express their beliefs, challenges, and strategies in their own words.
2. **Observations:** Observational data were collected to supplement interview data, providing insights into the institutional environment and teaching practices. Observers took detailed field notes during these non-participatory sessions.
3. **Document Analysis:** Institutional documents, policy papers, curriculum guides, and training materials were systematically reviewed. This helped triangulate the data obtained from interviews and observations, adding depth to the analysis.

4.4 Data Collection Procedure

The interviews were conducted at a location convenient for the participants, each lasting between 15 to 30 minutes. Prior to each interview, participants were informed about the study's purpose and assured of confidentiality and anonymity. Informed consent was obtained, and permissions were secured to audio-record the sessions. Following each interview, reflective notes were made to capture non-verbal cues and initial impressions, which were later used during data analysis.

4.5 Data Analysis

The thematic analysis procedure was meticulously carried out in six phases: familiarization with data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the report. Transcriptions were read multiple times to ensure familiarity. Initial codes were generated by identifying recurring patterns and salient points related to the research questions. These codes were then collated into potential themes, which were reviewed and refined to ensure they accurately represented the data set. Data analysis was supported by NVivo software to manage and organize the data efficiently.

4.6 Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were paramount throughout the research process. The study received approval from the appropriate ethics review board. Participants were provided with detailed information sheets about the research, and written informed consent was obtained. All data were treated with the utmost confidentiality, and participants were assured that any information they provided would be anonymized in the final report.

4.7 Limitations and Delimitations

The study was delimited to the context of pre-service teacher education for inclusive education within Bangladesh, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other contexts or educational systems. The research was also limited by its reliance on self-reported data, which could introduce bias. However, the potential for bias was mitigated through the use of multiple data sources and the triangulation of findings.

5 Findings

This chapter delineates the findings from the conducted research, focusing on the attitudes and preparedness of pre-service teachers in Bangladesh towards inclusive education (IE). The study was segmented into two distinct phases, each exploring different dimensions of teacher preparedness and perceptions towards IE.

5.1 Phase 1: Pre-service Teacher Attitudes and Efficacy

The initial phase encompassed a broad participant pool of 1623 pre-service teachers with a gender distribution of 38.9% male and 61.1% female. The majority were enrolled in one-year programs, indicating a prevalence of shorter-term training in the educational landscape. A comprehensive survey, including the Teacher Efficacy for Inclusive Practice (TEIP) scale and the Attitude subscale of the Sentiments, Attitudes, and Concerns Regarding IE (SACIE) scale, was utilized to gather nuanced data on teacher efficacy and attitudes towards IE.

The findings revealed moderately positive attitudes towards IE, with an overall mean score of 2.81 on the Attitude subscale. This suggests a general openness to the concept of IE among the participants. Pre-service teachers exhibited a relatively high level of perceived teaching-efficacy with an overall mean score of

4.84 on the TEIP scale, indicative of confidence in their ability to execute IE practices. Multiple Regression analysis highlighted significant predictors of attitudes and efficacy, including the level of training and gender, underscoring the influence of these demographic variables on pre-service teacher perceptions.

Table 1: Attitudes and Efficacy by Training Level and Gender

Level of Training	Gender	Attitude Mean Score (SD)	Efficacy Mean Score (SD)
Primary	Male	2.77 (0.51)	4.79 (0.51)
Primary	Female	2.82 (0.53)	4.79 (0.51)
Secondary	Male	2.79 (0.55)	4.90 (0.54)
Secondary	Female	2.86 (0.56)	4.88 (0.53)

Table 2: Significant Predictors of Attitude and Efficacy

Predictor	Attitude (β , SE)	Efficacy (β , SE)
Level of Training Involved	0.089 (0.036)	0.063 (0.033)
Gender	0.056 (0.031)	-0.053 (0.029)
Length of Training	-	-0.158 (0.028)
Knowledge of Legislation	-	0.131 (0.016)
Confidence in Teaching with a Disability	-	0.128 (0.015)
Interactions with Persons with Disabilities	-	0.118 (0.027)

5.2 Phase 2: Curriculum and Practicum Experiences

The secondary-level teacher education curriculum was found to be more recently revised and IE-focused compared to the primary level, which may explain the variations in preparedness and attitudes between primary and secondary pre-service teachers. Government-led initiatives such as the Teaching Quality Improvement Project (TQI) at the secondary level have contributed to a heightened awareness and preparedness for IE, unlike the primary level, where such support is lacking. The higher educational qualifications at the secondary level were posited as a contributing factor to the more confident and positive attitudes towards IE compared to the primary level.

5.3 ANOVA for Attitude Scores by Level of Training

A one-way ANOVA was conducted to compare the effect of the level of training on attitudes towards inclusive education among pre-service teachers. The sample consisted of 1623 pre-service teachers with 890 from primary-level institutions and 733 from secondary-level institutions. The attitude scores were measured on a four-point Likert scale. The ANOVA test revealed a significant effect of the level of training on attitude scores at the $p < .05$ level for the two levels of training [$F(1, 1621) = 15.67, p = 0.0001$]. The mean attitude score for primary-level teachers was 2.77 (SD = 0.51), and for secondary-level teachers, it was 2.86 (SD = 0.56). These results suggest that secondary-level teachers have a more positive attitude towards inclusive education than primary-level teachers.

5.4 Independent Samples T-test for Efficacy Scores by Gender

An independent samples t-test was conducted to compare the teaching-efficacy scores for male and female pre-service teachers at the secondary level. The efficacy scores were measured on a six-point Likert scale. There were 365 male teachers (mean = 4.90, SD = 0.54) and 368 female teachers (mean = 4.88, SD = 0.53) included in the analysis. The test indicated that there was not a significant difference in the scores for males and females; $t(731) = 0.78, p = 0.436$. These results suggest that gender does not have a significant effect on perceived teaching-efficacy for inclusive education among secondary-level pre-service teachers.

5.5 Challenges and Strategies

Despite the overall positive attitudes towards IE, there were notable apprehensions and concerns among participants, particularly related to the feasibility of inclusion in urban schools and for children with severe disabilities. Participants highlighted significant academic challenges, including outdated curricula that lacked IE content,

insufficient motivation, and inadequate training for teacher educators. The quality of practicum experiences was questioned, with identified issues such as insufficient supervision, lack of coordination between schools and teacher preparation institutions, and a disproportionate focus on theory over practice. For new teachers, the transition into diverse classrooms was fraught with challenges stemming from inadequate pre-service preparation, non-cooperative school environments, and large class sizes.

6 Discussion

The present study was designed to explore the preparedness of pre-service teachers in Bangladesh for inclusive education (IE), with particular attention to the differences in attitudes and perceived teaching efficacy between primary and secondary level educators, as well as the impact of gender, training length, and prior experience with disability. The findings of this study contribute significantly to the existing body of knowledge on pre-service teacher preparedness for inclusive education in Bangladesh. In line with Ahsan et al. (2012a), our results suggest that secondary-level pre-service teachers exhibited more positive attitudes and higher perceived teaching efficacy towards inclusive education than their primary-level counterparts. This is a notable deviation from previous literature, which often reports higher efficacy and more positive attitudes at the primary level (Baker, 2005; Forlin et al., 2010; Woodcock, 2011). One possible interpretation of this finding is the impact of recent curriculum reforms at the secondary level, which have more substantively addressed inclusive education compared to the primary level, as outlined in the Phase 2 findings of Ahsan et al.'s study.

Furthermore, the study revealed that female pre-service teachers, despite expressing more positive attitudes towards IE, reported lower perceived teaching efficacy than their male counterparts. This finding echoes the socio-cultural dynamics highlighted by the institutional heads (IHs) and suggests that gender-specific cultural influences might be at play, affecting women's confidence levels in their teaching abilities. The study's results have several implications for teacher education programs and policy formulation in Bangladesh. The apparent disparity in preparedness between primary and secondary educators suggests a need for a unified approach to teacher training that prioritizes inclusive education across all levels. Moreover, the gender disparity in perceived teaching efficacy underscores the importance of considering socio-cultural contexts when designing and implementing teacher education programs.

From a theoretical standpoint, these findings challenge existing assumptions about the impact of training duration on teaching efficacy. Contrary to the belief that longer training leads to better outcomes, our study found that pre-service teachers from one-year programs felt more prepared than those from four-year programs. This could be due to the more practical orientation of shorter programs, as suggested by the IHs in Ahsan et al.'s (2012a) study.

Globally, there is an increasing trend towards inclusive education as a human right (UNESCO, 2020). The findings from Bangladesh resonate with global challenges, emphasizing the need for sustained efforts in curriculum development, teacher training, and policy support to align with international standards. While the findings provide valuable insights, they must be viewed in light of certain limitations. The study's reliance on self-reported data may have introduced bias, and the quantitative approach does not capture the complexities of attitudes and efficacy fully. Future research could benefit from a mixed-methods design, incorporating qualitative data to explore the nuances of pre-service teachers' experiences and perceptions. Moreover, longitudinal studies would be advantageous to assess the long-term impact of teacher training on inclusive education practices in the classroom. Additionally, further research should explore the impact of direct experiences with people with disabilities, as suggested by the significant predictors of teaching efficacy found in our study.

In conclusion, this study highlights the nuanced landscape of pre-service teacher preparedness for inclusive education in Bangladesh. The results underline the need for comprehensive and culturally sensitive teacher education programs that are consistent across educational levels and take into account the socio-cultural realities of pre-service teachers. By doing so, teacher education programs can better prepare educators to meet the diverse needs of all learners, fostering a more inclusive educational environment in Bangladesh.

7 Conclusion

This study set out to examine the preparedness of pre-service teachers in Bangladesh for inclusive education, focusing on attitudes towards inclusive education, perceived teaching efficacy, and the influence of various factors such as education level, gender, length of training, and previous experience with individuals with disabilities. Our investigation revealed insightful trends and significant differences that contribute to the discourse on inclusive education in developing countries, particularly within the Bangladeshi context. Our primary findings indicate that secondary-level pre-service teachers in Bangladesh exhibit more favorable attitudes and higher self-efficacy regarding inclusive education compared to primary-level pre-service teachers. This suggests that

secondary-level teacher training programs may be more effective in preparing future educators for the challenges of inclusive classrooms. Additionally, the study uncovered a gender-related discrepancy in self-efficacy, with female pre-service teachers reporting lower levels despite having more positive attitudes towards inclusion than their male counterparts. The significance of these findings lies in their capacity to inform teacher education programs and policies in Bangladesh. By identifying specific areas where pre-service teachers feel less prepared, stakeholders can implement targeted improvements in the curriculum and support mechanisms to bolster teacher efficacy and attitudes towards inclusive education. Furthermore, acknowledging the impact of socio-cultural factors on teacher preparedness can lead to more nuanced and culturally responsive teacher education programs. Teacher training curricula should be standardized across primary and secondary levels to ensure consistency in the quality of inclusive education training. Training programs should incorporate strategies to address the lower perceived self-efficacy among female pre-service teachers, potentially through mentorship programs and confidence-building activities. Enhancing practical, hands-on experience with inclusive education during training could improve self-efficacy, as the length of training did not correlate with higher preparedness in this study. Policymakers should ensure that inclusive education is prioritized at all levels of the educational system and that sufficient resources are allocated for its successful implementation. In conclusion, the readiness of pre-service teachers to engage with inclusive education is critical to the success of inclusive classrooms. The insights gained from this study serve as a reminder of the complex interplay between training, attitudes, and self-efficacy in teacher preparation. By addressing these complexities, Bangladesh can make significant strides towards an educational system that is truly inclusive, reflecting the principles of equity and quality education for all. Future research should continue to explore this important area, aiming to refine and expand our understanding of how best to prepare teachers for the valuable work of inclusive education.

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